

Supporting Information for

Air quality and health effects of U.S. energy transitions

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Extended Methods

S1. Activity Modeling and Air Pollution Emissions

This section outlines the activity and emissions estimation approaches used for each source category. Across categories, we draw on different levels of methodological detail depending on data availability, each category's contribution to total emissions, and the characteristics of the emissions involved. We begin with macro-energy system modeling, using EnergyPATHWAYS to simulate state-level demand and the Regional Investment and Operations (RIO) model to optimize the regional supply portfolio required to meet that demand (1). We downscale activity and emissions from regional and state resolutions to county resolutions.

For some source categories, we use the approach describe in Mayfield & Jenkins (2) and used in Jenkins et al. (3), which report primary fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxide (NO_x), and volatile organic compound (VOC) emissions but do not include ammonia (NH₃) emissions. We impute NH₃ emissions for modeled sectors using derived scaling factors that relate modeled NO_x emissions to NO_x emissions in the 2017 Emissions Modeling Platform (4), which are based on data from the 2017 National Emissions Inventory (NEI) (5). NO_x scaling factors are derived for each combination of sector, year, scenario, and county. Scaling factors are then multiplied by county-level 2017 modeling platform NH₃ emissions to produce NH₃ emission estimates for all sectors, scenarios, and years analyzed in this study. Fig. S2 shows emission totals for all years, scenarios, and sectors.

Electric Power. Emission rates for coal and natural gas electricity generation for NO_x and SO₂ are derived using emissions and generation data by technology (i.e. prime mover) and fuel type from the 2021 Emissions and Generation Resource Integrated Database (eGRID) (6). Data for coal fuel types and grouped, as are natural gas fuel types. Two prime mover types, combined cycle steam turbine and combined cycle combustion turbine, are combined to represent total unit-level emissions and generation for combined cycle generators. Unit-level emissions data and generator-level generation data are then aggregated to the plant level. Consistent with eGRID methodology, we derive adjustment factors to isolate the portion of plant-level emissions that do not result from biomass/biogas generation; eGRID assumes that gas from a landfill that is combusted for electricity generation otherwise would have been flared at a landfill and emissions should not be attributed to electricity generation (7). For combined heat and power facilities, emissions are also multiplied by provided plant-level electric allocation factors to isolate the portion of emissions attributable to electricity generation. These adjusted emission data and generation data are then aggregated by state, technology, and fuel type to derive state-level emission rates. National

emission rates are also calculated by aggregating emissions and generation data across all states to impute missing state-level emission rates.

Emission rates for coal and natural gas electricity generation for primary PM_{2.5}, VOCs, and NH₃ are derived using unit-level emission rate data from EPA (8). Office of Regulatory Information Systems (ORIS) plant codes and unit identifiers are extracted from the National Electricity Energy Data System (NEEDS) unique identifier field provided in the dataset; data are then mapped to eGRID generator-level data using ORIS plant codes and unit identifiers. Primary PM_{2.5}, VOC, and NH₃ emissions from coal and natural gas electricity are simulated by multiplying emission rates by eGRID generator-level generation totals; state-level and national emission rates are then derived by aggregating data in the same manner as for NO_x and SO₂.

Newly derived state-level emission rates for all pollutants are mapped to state-level generation data by technology and fuel types. Generation data from Jenkins et al. (3), reported by electricity market module region, are assigned to the state level using the downscaling approach from Jones et al. (9). Modeled state-level emission totals are simulated by multiplying generation totals by emission rates. State-level emission totals for both sectors are then assigned to counties in direct proportion to each county and pollutant's portion of state-level emissions in the 2017 emissions modeling platform. For counties with more than one plant per sector, we calculate emission-weighted average stack heights that are used to represent all plants in a county.

Transportation. To derive emissions from on-road vehicles, data on modeled vehicle population and vehicle miles traveled (VMTs) from EnergyPATHWAYS are combined with emission rates, which we calculate from data in the 2021 Emissions Modeling Platform (10). The 2021 emissions modeling platform is used in place of the 2017 emissions modeling platform for on-road sectors because the 2021 platform provides data for more vehicle- and fuel-type combinations (that are required for this study) and because, between the development of the 2017 and 2020 NEIs, updates were made to the Motor Vehicle Emissions Simulator (MOVES) that modified estimates of on-road vehicle emission rates used in the NEI and emissions modeling platforms (11).

We derive emission rates for on-road vehicles using county-level data on vehicle populations, VMTs, and emissions provided in the 2021 emissions modeling platform. Emission rates are derived for all on-roadway and off-network emission processes in the emissions modeling platform:

- Rate per distance (grams per mile): running exhaust; crankcase running exhaust; tire wear; brake wear; on-road evaporative permeation, fuel leaks, and vapor venting
- Rate per vehicle (grams per vehicle per hour): start exhaust; crankcase start exhaust; off-network evaporative permeation and fuel leaks; crankcase extended idle exhaust; and extended idle exhaust
- Rate per profile (grams per vehicle per hour): off-network evaporative fuel vapor venting
- Rate per hour (grams per hour): on-roadway extended idle exhaust
- Rate per start (grams per start): off-network engine start exhaust
- Off-network idling (grams per hour): off-network idling

Modifications to modeled vehicle population and VMT data are required before we can determine emission totals. VMT and vehicle population data are initially provided at the state level in our modeled datasets; modeled VMTs and vehicle population data are assigned to counties in direct proportion to a county's portion of state VMTs or vehicle population in the 2021 emissions modeling platform datasets. The apportionment of VMTs is based on each vehicle type and road type combination since rate-per-distance emission rates are assumed to differ depending on whether a mile is traveled on an urban/rural roadway with restricted (i.e. accessed by an on-ramp) or unrestricted access (11). Our modeled activity data do not distinguish between passenger trucks and light commercial trucks, single-unit and combination short-haul trucks, or single-unit and combination long-haul trucks. Since emission rates are different for these vehicle types, similar to county apportionment, we sum vehicle population and VMTs in the 2021 emissions modeling platform for each of these vehicle type pairings by county and apportion grouped VMT and vehicle population data proportionally. For example, if 90% of miles traveled by light-duty trucks (i.e. passenger trucks and light commercial trucks) are traveled by passenger trucks, 90% of VMTs are apportioned to light-duty trucks to passenger trucks and 10% to light commercial trucks.

Data on hoteling hours, which refers to the extended idling of long-haul combination truck engines and the use of auxiliary power units (i.e. small onboard power generators) during driver rest periods, are updated to reflect changes in the annual number of hours per county that diesel long-haul combination trucks spend idling. We calculate the average number of hours per truck per county from the 2021 emissions modeling platform and multiply this by the number of trucks in future years to calculate the total number of hours per county. We assume that electric long-haul combination trucks will be equipped with electric auxiliary power units and therefore produce no hoteling emissions.

Consistent with MOVES methodology, we assume that gasoline and diesel hybrid vehicles have the same emission profiles as their gasoline or diesel equivalents and that liquid hydrogen fuel cell vehicles share emission profiles with electric vehicles (11). We also assume that LNG vehicles have the same emission profiles as CNG vehicles. We also assume that medium-duty trucks, which are included in our modeled dataset but not in MOVES, correspond to short-haul single unit trucks. The 2021 emissions modeling platform does not include rate-per-distance emission rates for all electric vehicle types necessary for our analysis. These electric vehicle types include intercity buses, school buses, single unit short-haul trucks, single unit long-haul trucks, combination short-haul trucks, and combination long-haul trucks. Emission rates for these vehicle types are computed by assigning the emission rates for tire wear and brake wear for their diesel equivalents. Emissions from refueling, exhaust, and evaporative emissions are set to zero. Table S1 provides a breakdown of existing and newly created emission rates.

Residential and Commercial Sources. We simulate emissions associated with fuel combustion in the residential and commercial sectors following the approach used in Jenkins et al. (3). We begin with county-level emissions reported in the 2017 NEI that are associated with residential and commercial combustion of coal, natural gas, oil (i.e. kerosene, residual oil, distillate oil, diesel), and other fuels (i.e., coal, gasoline, liquefied petroleum gas [LPG]). Using annual, state-level fuel consumption reported in the State Energy Data Systems (SEDS), we scale 2017 emissions to 2019 (12). To project future emissions from 2022 to 2050, we scale 2019 emissions using annual, state-level, residential and commercial sector fuel demand projections, including

coal, natural gas, oil, and other fuel consumption associated with heating, cooling, cooking, and other demands specified in EnergyPATHWAYS.

Fuel Production. We simulate annual, county-level coal production from underground and surface mines, following the approach used in Jenkins et al. (3). We assume that the United States continues to produce coal to meet domestic industrial and coking demand as well as projected exports. Continued coal production to meet export demand is assumed to occur in states that have historically produced coal for export; we use 2019 historical state origin of exports to spatially allocate future production at the state level (13). To spatially allocate underground and surface production to the county level, we use mine-level data reported for 2017 and 2019 (14). We model point and non-point emissions associated with coal mining. We use emissions reported in the 2017 NEI for coal point sources (NAICS 2121 coal mining, 212111 Bituminous Coal and Lignite Surface Mining, 212112 Bituminous Coal Underground Mining) (5). We project county-level point source emissions from 2022 to 2050 for each scenario using scaling factors based on future annual surface and underground production relative to production in 2017 for each county. We also estimate nonpoint source industrial process emissions associated with coal mining operations, including fugitive emissions from overburden removal, drilling and blasting, loading and unloading, and overburden replacement activities, assuming an emissions factor (0.064 pounds PM_{2.5} per ton of surface coal production) reported in the 2017 NEI (5).

We simulate annual, county-level emissions from associated with oil and gas production, following the approach used in Jenkins et al. (3). We use county-level emissions (including venting, fugitive, flaring, other combustion, and other process emissions) reported in the 2017 NEI associated with all upstream oil and gas exploration, extraction, and storage processes (5). Using annual, state-level oil and gas production reported by the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA), we scale 2017 emissions to 2020 (15, 16). To project future emissions, we scale 2020 emissions using state-level oil and gas production projections. We then convert projected nationwide oil and gas production to states based on historical spatial distributions (15, 16). We assume that the United States will continue to export oil and gas at rates consistent with the EIA Annual Energy Outlook 2020 reference case projection (17). As domestic oil consumption declines, we assume that the United States will import less oil and that a higher share of oil will be produced domestically but will not be in excess of projected domestic crude production. We also assume that the United States produces enough natural gas to meet domestic and export demand (17).

S2. Air Quality Modeling

APSCA is based on the Estimating Air Pollution Social Impacts Using Regression (EASIUR) model (18), which estimates the social costs of PM_{2.5} components (i.e. monetized PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality damages per ton of emissions) at emission source locations. APSCA builds on EASIUR by allowing for the resolution of social costs at receptor locations; this is done using a chemical transport model, Comprehensive Air Quality model with extensions (CAMx), to map the spatial distribution of emissions from 50 random locations in the contiguous United States. PM_{2.5} concentrations from CAMx are normalized to derive an “average plume” for these training locations whereby weighted fractions of social costs from any source grid cell can be assigned to downwind receptor grid cells. APSCA resolves PM_{2.5} concentrations at a 36 km × 36 km

resolution. APSCA estimates concentrations from inorganic PM_{2.5} components (i.e. inert primary PM_{2.5}, SO₂, NO_x, and NH₃) but does not cover primary organic PM_{2.5} or VOCs. Despite this, we include APSCA to assess the effects of the choice of air quality model on health outcomes, inheriting all model limitations.

COBRA (version 4.7) uses a source–receptor matrix based on the Climatological Regional Dispersion Model, itself similar to an EPA-recommended Gaussian dispersion model (19), which provides a simplified relationship between emissions of primary PM_{2.5} and gaseous precursors (i.e. SO₂, NO_x, NH₃, and VOCs) at a source location and ambient PM_{2.5} concentrations at a receptor location, accounting for wet and dry deposition, mixing heights, wind speed, meteorology, and chemical conversion of secondary PM_{2.5} components at receptor locations (20). COBRA resolves PM_{2.5} concentrations at the county level. We use the 2023 source–receptor matrix and adjustment parameters for all model runs.

ISRM is based on the Intervention Model for Air Pollution (InMAP) (21, 22), which uses output from a chemical transport model, the Weather Research and Forecasting model coupled with Chemistry (WRF-Chem), and makes simplifying assumptions about atmospheric chemistry to estimate PM_{2.5} concentrations based on annual emissions. ISRM represents a series of source–receptor matrices based on marginal PM_{2.5} concentration changes from emissions of primary PM_{2.5}, SO₂, NO_x, NH₃, and VOCs at source locations in InMAP. ISRM resolves PM_{2.5} concentrations using variable grid cell sizes based on population density, ranging from 1 km × 1 km (densely populated) to 48 km × 48 km (sparsely populated).

Each model is run in succession with emission data for each year, scenario, and sector in our emission dataset. Emission data are modified to conform to model formatting needs. COBRA takes emission inputs grouped by Emission Inventory System (EIS) tiers instead of SCC or sector. For each tier grouping and county, we calculate an emission-weighted average stack height from facility stack heights in the emission inventories, which is used to set the appropriate effective stack height in COBRA. Point sources are set to low (0–250 m), medium (250–500 m), or high (>500 m) depending on emission-weighted stack heights, while nonpoint and on-road sectors are set to ground-level area sources (0 m). Wildfire and prescribed fire emissions are set to low emission sources. County-level emission data (with emission-weighted stack height data) derived for use in COBRA are then spatially allocated to APSCA and ISRM grid definitions using an area-weighting approach.

We assess inter-model differences in the spatial distribution of concentration changes in modeled scenarios using the Jensen–Shannon divergence (JSD) (23). The JSD has been used previously in studies of meteorology (24) and air quality (25, 26). JSD values range from 0 (perfect agreement) to 1 (perfect disagreement). Within a given year and scenario, we order distributions by ascending model-average concentration change so that the probability distributions for all models reflect the same county ordering.

S3. Health Impact Modeling

This work uses newly derived racial/ethnic–stratified baseline mortality rate data. We calculate future-year all-cause (and non-accidental) mortality rates for each county, age, and race/ethnicity as follows:

$$y_{i,j,k}^{x_1} = y_{i,j,k}^{x_0} \times \frac{y_{j,k}^{x_1}}{\bar{y}_{j,k}^{x_0}} \quad (1)$$

where x_0 refers to 2018–2022, x_1 is a future year, \bar{y} is the nationwide population-weighted average mortality rate, and y is the mortality rate for county i , age group j , and racial/ethnic group k . U.S. Census Bureau mortality rate projections are available for three racial/ethnic groups: “non-Hispanic White and Asian or Pacific Islander,” “non-Hispanic Black and American Indian or Alaska Native,” and “Hispanic.” We apply relevant ratios to each of the five racial/ethnic groups used in the rest of our analysis. U.S. Census Bureau mortality projections do not include non-accidental mortality, so we scale non-accidental mortality rates by all-cause mortality rate ratios to derive future-year non-accidental mortality rates. We expect error introduced by this method to be small since non-accidental mortality accounts for the vast majority of deaths in the United States. We do not differentiate mortality rates by sex or nativity (i.e. native or foreign born).

We use the Global Exposure Mortality Model (GEMM) function (27) as the primary exposure–response function in the main text. The GEMM function takes the form:

$$HR(x) = e^{0.143 \left(\frac{\ln\left(\frac{\max(0, x-2.4)+1}{1.6}\right)}{1+e^{\frac{-\max(0, x-2.4)-15.5}{36.8}}}\right)} \quad (2)$$

where $HR(x)$ is the hazard ratio of mortality incidence at $PM_{2.5}$ concentration x . The fraction of deaths attributable to $PM_{2.5}$ exposure (AF) is defined as:

$$AF = \frac{HR(x)-1}{HR(x)} \quad (3)$$

The number of $PM_{2.5}$ -attributable deaths is then calculated as:

$$M = AF \cdot y \cdot pop \quad (4)$$

where M is the number of deaths, y is the mortality rate, and pop is the population count in a given county. We also estimate mortality burdens using exposure–response functions from Turner et al. (28), Pope et al. (29), and Lepeule et al. (30). These functions all take the form:

$$HR(x) = e^{\beta x} \quad (5)$$

where $\beta = 0.005826891$ for Turner et al. (28), 0.01133 for Pope et al. (29), and 0.013102826 for Lepeule et al. (30).

S4. Economic Valuation

We determine the monetized value of changes in PM_{2.5}-related mortality using EPA's recommended central estimate of the value of a statistical life (VSL), \$7.4 million (2006 U.S. dollars) (31), which we inflation-adjust to 2022 U.S. dollars (\$10.7 million). Uncertainty in monetized values is based on a Weibull distribution of 26 VSL estimates that is used in BenMAP-CE (31) and has the following probability density function:

$$\left(\frac{\beta}{\alpha}\right) \times \left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \times e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta}} \quad (6)$$

where $\alpha = 9,648,168$ (2015 U.S. dollars) and $\beta = 1.509588$. We assume no cessation lag between exposure and mortality (i.e. deaths occur in the year of exposure). Monetized values in the main text assume no discounting in future years; we include sensitivities with discount rates of 2% and 3% in the SI Appendix, section S9. Uncertainty in monetized estimates is characterized using a Monte Carlo simulation approach that accounts for uncertainty in the VSL estimate and the hazard ratio function.

S5. Decomposition Analysis

To decompose the effects of population growth, population aging, baseline mortality rate changes, and PM_{2.5} exposure changes on changes in nationwide PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality totals in 2035 and 2050 relative to 2022, we use a modified version of a method from the 2015 Global Burden of Disease study (32) that has been used in other air quality studies (33). Calculations used in this method are as follows:

$$A = \sum pop_{i,j,k}^{x_1} \times \frac{\sum (y_{i,j,k}^{x_0} \times pop_{i,j,k}^{x_0})}{\sum pop_{i,j,k}^{x_0}} \times AF_{i,all-age,k}^{x_0} \quad (7)$$

$$B = \sum (y_{i,j,k}^{x_0} \times pop_{i,j,k}^{x_1} \times AF_{i,j,k}^{x_0}) \quad (8)$$

$$C = \sum \left(pop_{i,j,k}^{x_0} \times y_{i,j,k}^{x_1} \times \left(\frac{1 - AF_{i,j,k}^{x_1}}{1 - AF_{i,j,k}^{x_0}} \right) \times AF_{i,j,k}^{x_0} \right) \quad (9)$$

where *pop* is the population count for county *i*, age group *j*, and racial/ethnic group *k*, *x₀* is 2022, *x₁* is a future year, *y* is the mortality rate, and *AF* is the fraction of deaths attributable to PM_{2.5} exposure. Given equations 7–9, the percent contribution of each factor for racial/ethnic group *k* is then given as:

$$\text{Population growth effect} = \frac{A - M_k^{x_0}}{M_k^{x_0}} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Population aging effect} = \frac{B - A}{M_k^{x_0}} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{Baseline mortality rate change effect} = \frac{C - B}{M_k^{x_0}} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Exposure change effect} = \frac{M_k^{x_1 - C}}{M_k^{x_0}} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{Total change} = \frac{M_k^{x_1} - M_k^{x_0}}{M_k^{x_0}} \quad (14)$$

where M is the nationwide PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality burden, given in equation 4. Decomposed effects are calculated for the total population by repeating calculations using versions of equations 4 and 7–14 that do not differentiate by race/ethnicity.

S6. Racial/Ethnic Disparity Analysis

We convert PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality counts into age-adjusted mortality rates for each racial/ethnic using the direct method with the 2000 U.S. standard population as the reference population (34). Adjustment weights are calculated for five-year age groups from 25–84 years and for 85+ years.

We use the Gini coefficient to assess inequality in the distribution of avoided mortality benefits by race/ethnicity. Gini coefficients are derived from Lorenz curves for all years, scenarios, models, and racial/ethnic groups shown in Fig. S15. For each year, scenario, model, and racial/ethnic group, Lorenz curves are drawn by plotting county-level population count against county-level avoided mortality total with data ordering by ascending per-capita avoided mortality benefits, which is calculated by dividing county-level avoided mortality totals by the county-level population count. Counties with negative avoided mortality totals for a given racial/ethnic group are excluded from this analysis.

Extended Results

S7. Mortality Rate Data Evaluation

Fig. S16 shows probability distributions for BenMAP–CE default 2007–2016 all-cause mortality rate data for White and non-White population groups and our newly derived race/ethnicity–stratified mortality data using 2018–2022 mortality rates. Data for all non-White racial/ethnic groups in newly derived datasets are combined to allow for comparison to BenMAP–CE data; data for five-year age groups are also combined to ten-year age groups to conform to BenMAP–CE groupings. Despite the update to more recent years, mortality rate data are similarly distributed in both datasets (Fig. S16), particularly for older age groups; given that older age groups have much higher mortality rates, differences between datasets among older age groups would disproportionately skew attributable mortality totals for the total population.

Probability distributions for BenMAP–CE default and newly derived mortality rate data in present and future years for the total population for all-cause mortality and non-accidental mortality are shown in Fig. S17 and S18, respectively. (Comparisons of newly derived mortality rate data to BenMAP–CE defaults for rates stratified by race/ethnicity are not possible since BenMAP–CE does not include these data.) Newly derived mortality rate data in these figures are aggregated in the same way as data in Fig. S16, except that all racial/ethnic groups are aggregated to reflect the

total population. The largely overlapping distributions in Figs. S16–18 indicate that the use of our newly derived mortality rates does not introduce substantial error in mortality count estimates relative to using BenMAP–CE data. Table S2 compares nationwide attributable mortality totals in 2022 using default BenMAP–CE mortality rates and newly derived mortality rates stratified by race/ethnicity; across the three air quality models, new totals differ from default totals by ~2% when using Burnett et al. (27) with unstratified default rates and differ by ~11% and ~6%, respectively, when using Turner et al. (28) with unstratified and stratified default rates.

S8. Air Quality Impacts

Comparisons of probability distributions using the JSD are based on both raw and normalized county-level concentration changes, with normalized changes isolating differences in spatial patterns independent of differences in magnitude (Fig. S5). Normalized distributions of each pair of models are generally more similar in the net-zero scenario than in the IRA scenario, and normalized distributions tend to be more similar than raw distributions.

Given normalized values, the distributions of each pair of models are generally more similar in 2035 in the net-zero scenario (JSD range: 0.012–0.054) than in the IRA scenario (0.006–0.181), except for APSCA and ISRM in the IRA scenario, which have the most similar distribution (0.006) of any model combination using normalized or raw values. Similarities between models tend to be lower when using raw values, except for APSCA and COBRA in the IRA scenario in 2035 and 2050 as well as APSCA and ISRM in the IRA scenario in 2050. In 2050, distributions are more similar in the net-zero scenario (0.012–0.054) than the IRA scenario (0.105–0.432) when using normalized distributions but less similar in the net-zero scenario (0.118–0.302) than the IRA scenario (0.076–0.250) when using raw distributions, in part because of the constrained concentration changes in the IRA scenario in 2050.

S9. Monetized Benefit and Cost Comparison

Federal budget outlays related to the climate and energy provisions of the IRA have been estimated by the U.S. Congressional Budget Office to be \$379 billion (2022 U.S. dollars) from 2022–2031 as a result of direct spending on climate-related programs and reduced public revenue from tax credit programs (35). Over the same period, cumulative benefits from avoided mortality total \$114 billion (CI: \$11–299 billion) in the IRA scenario (Table S3); this indicates that the PM_{2.5}-related health benefits from the climate and energy provisions of the IRA could have offset a sizable portion of public costs but that benefits would not have exceeded costs in the near term.

Monetized benefit totals are sensitive to the choice of discount rate. Results above and in the main text assume no discounting in future years. Table S3 compares monetized benefits using 0%, 2%, and 3% annual discount rates. Using 2% and 3% discount rates, cumulative monetized PM_{2.5}-related health benefits of the IRA from 2022–2050 would not have exceeded federal tax credit net expenditures, whereas they would have when using a 0% discount rate.

S10. Uncertainty Analysis

Despite its relatively minor importance when considering the overall population, stratifying mortality rates by race/ethnicity has meaningful and variable effects on the portion of benefits experienced by a given racial/ethnic group (Table S4). The use of stratified mortality rates decreases the portion of benefits experienced by Asian, Hispanic, and Native Americans since mortality rates among these groups are lower in the overall population; the use of stratified mortality rates increases the portion of benefits experienced by Black and White Americans.

S11. Decomposition Analysis

Across years, baseline PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality totals differ by 6–13% across models (Fig. S8), indicating that APSCA, COBRA, and ISRM report more similar estimates of attributable PM_{2.5} mortality than avoidable PM_{2.5} mortality. The pronounced role of population growth and aging among Asian and Hispanic populations in determining attributable PM_{2.5} mortality is evident in the fact that these population groups receive increasing shares of avoided PM_{2.5} mortality benefits in the IRA and net-zero scenarios over time (Table S4). In the IRA (and net-zero) scenarios, Asian and Hispanic populations respectively experience 4.0% (3.4%) and 10% (9.0%) of total avoided premature deaths in 2035; these portions increase to 7.3% (5.6%) and 16% (15%) by 2050. The share of benefits experienced by Black (13–14%) and Native populations (<1%) are consistent across years and scenarios. White populations experience a decreasing share of avoided mortality benefits over time in the IRA (and net-zero) scenarios: 73% (74%) in 2035 and 62% (66%) in 2050.

S12. Racial/Ethnic Disparity Analysis

The Gini coefficient (G) is a standard measure of inequality ranging from 0 (perfect equality) to 1 (perfect inequality). For a given year and racial/ethnic group, variation in Gini coefficients across models and scenarios is attributable solely to the distribution and magnitude of PM_{2.5} concentration changes since the size, age structure, geographic distribution, and baseline mortality rates of population groups are identical. However, when comparing inequality across racial/ethnic groups within a given year, differences reflect both variation in concentration changes and the distribution of racial/ethnic groups across the United States. Gini coefficients for all years, scenarios, models, and racial/ethnic groups are shown in Fig. S14.

Distributions of health benefits in the overall population are similarly unequal in 2035 in the IRA ($G = 0.34$) and net-zero ($G = 0.37$) scenarios, assuming model-averaged concentration changes (Fig. S14). By 2050, inequality increases in IRA scenario ($G = 0.42$) but remains nearly constant in the net-zero scenario ($G = 0.48$), suggesting that the net-zero pathway yields persistently unequal benefits, whereas the IRA could have produced more equitable outcomes while its provisions were to be active. These differences highlight how policy design and implementation influence the distribution of health benefits. Estimates by race/ethnicity diverge modestly across air quality models in 2050; benefits are more unequally distributed across racial/ethnic groups in the IRA scenario than the net-zero scenario when using APSCA and COBRA, while ISRM yields similar values across scenarios (Fig. S14).

Fig. S1. Conceptual diagram of the integrated modeling framework.

Fig. S2. Emissions by sector and scenario for primary PM_{2.5} (fine particulate matter), SO₂ (sulfur dioxide), NO_x (nitrogen oxides), NH₃ (ammonia), and VOCs (volatile organic compounds). NEI values represent emission totals for the same sectors. Base-year NH₃ emissions differ from 2017 and 2020 NEI totals due to higher per-mile vehicle NH₃ emission rates available in the 2021 emissions modeling platform that we use to derive vehicle emissions that were not used in the development of either NEI.

Fig. S3. Primary PM_{2.5} emissions from vehicle exhaust and tire and brake wear.

Fig. S4. Individual monitoring sites are shown in the maps; monitoring data in scatterplots is averaged by county for counties with multiple monitoring sites. Linear trendlines are shown in red. MB = mean bias; ME = mean error; NMB = normalized mean bias; NME = normalized mean error; r = Pearson correlation coefficient.

Fig. S5. Probability distributions for normalized (left) and raw (right) concentration changes by year, scenario, and model. Concentration change data are ranked in ascending order of model-averaged concentration decreases. Colored numbers in right panels show population-weighted concentration decreases for each model.

Fig. S6. Sectoral breakdown of avoided premature deaths by year, scenario, sector, and exposure–response function.

Fig. S7. Effect of the choice of air quality model, choice of exposure–response function, and racial/ethnic stratification of baseline mortality rates on nationwide avoided PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths by year and scenario. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals that reflect uncertainty in the hazard ratio functions from Turner et al. (28), Burnett et al. (27), Pope et al. (29), and Lepeule et al. (30).

Fig. S8. PM_{2.5}-attributable deaths by year and model using the exposure–response function from Burnett et al. (27).

Fig. S9. Age-adjusted PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality rates in the overall population using the exposure–response function Burnett et al. (27).

Fig. S10. Disparities in age-adjusted PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality rates using the exposure–response function from Burnett et al. (27).

Fig. S11. Age-adjusted PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality rates in the overall population using the exposure–response function from Turner et al. (28).

Fig. S12. Age-adjusted PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality rates by race/ethnicity, year, and scenario. Values shown here use model-averaged concentration data and the exposure–response function from Turner et al. (28). Dotted lines in bar charts show values for the overall population.

Fig. S13. Disparities in age-adjusted PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality rates using the exposure–response function from Turner et al. (28).

Fig. S14. Inequality in the county-level distribution of avoided PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths by year, scenario, and model (left panels). Positive values in the right panel denote more unequal outcomes in the IRA than net-zero scenario; negative values denote less-unequal outcomes in the IRA scenario. Values shown here use the exposure–response function from Burnett et al. (27).

Fig. S15. Lorenz curves used to derived Gini coefficients. Values shown here use the exposure–response function from Burnett et al. (27).

Fig. S16. Probability distributions of county-level all-cause mortality rate data from BenMAP-CE and this study for non-White and White populations in 2007–2016 (default) and 2018–2022 (newly derived) by age group. Mortality rate data are ranked in ascending order of BenMAP-CE data.

Fig. S17. Probability distributions of county-level all-cause mortality rate data from BenMAP-CE and this study for the total population in present and future years by age group. Mortality rate data are ranked in ascending order of BenMAP-CE data.

Fig. S18. Probability distributions of county-level non-accidental mortality rate data from BenMAP-CE and this study for the total population in present and future years. Mortality rate data are ranked in ascending order of BenMAP-CE data.

Table S1. Vehicle–fuel combinations that use existing MOVES emission rates (✓), are not included in our study (–), and use newly derived emission rates (indicated by the reference fuel type used to derive them)

Vehicle type	Fuel type				
	Gasoline	Diesel	CNG	LPG	Electric
Passenger car	✓	✓	–	–	✓
Passenger truck	✓	✓	–	–	✓
Light commercial truck	✓	✓	–	–	✓
Intercity bus	–	✓	✓	–	Diesel
Transit bus	–	✓	✓	–	✓
School bus	–	✓	✓	–	Diesel
Single unit short-haul truck	✓	✓	–	–	Diesel
Single unit long-haul truck	✓	✓	–	–	Diesel
Combination short-haul truck	✓	✓	–	–	Diesel
Combination long-haul truck	–	✓	–	–	Diesel

Note: Elective vehicle emission rates derived from equivalent diesel vehicle rates apply only to tire and brake wear emission rates; exhaust emissions are set to zero.

Table S2. Nationwide PM_{2.5}-attributable deaths (thousands) in 2022 using default BenMAP-CE and newly derived mortality rates

Exposure– response function	Model	Default		Newly derived	Difference	
		Unstratified	Stratified		Unstratified	Stratified
Burnett et al. (2018)	APSCA	182 (CI: 160–204)	–	186 (CI: 163–208)	2.09%	–
	COBRA	180 (CI: 158–202)	–	184 (CI: 161–206)	1.85%	–
	ISRM	170 (CI: 150–191)	–	174 (CI: 153–195)	2.22%	–
Turner et al. (2016)	APSCA	103 (CI: 87–120)	108 (CI: 91–126)	115 (CI: 96–134)	11.4%	6.12%
	COBRA	99 (CI: 83–115)	104 (CI: 87–121)	110 (CI: 92–128)	11.3%	6.01%
	ISRM	98 (CI: 82–114)	103 (CI: 86–120)	110 (CI: 92–127)	11.8%	6.46%

Note: Differences are calculated using unrounded values.

Table S3. Cumulative monetized benefits using alternative discount rates (billion 2022 U.S. dollars)

Years	Scenario	Discount rate			Cost comparison
		0%	2%	3%	
2022–2050	IRA	\$1,407 (CI: \$138–3,713)	\$990 (CI: \$97–2,606)	\$837 (CI: \$83–2,208)	\$1,071 ^a
	Net Zero	\$2,967 (CI: \$292–7,824)	\$2,095 (CI: \$206–5,533)	\$1,779 (CI: \$175–4,694)	
2022–2031	IRA	\$113 (CI: \$11–299)	\$98 (CI: \$9.7–258)	\$91 (CI: \$9.0–240)	\$379 ^b
	Net Zero	\$462 (CI: \$46–1,218)	\$415 (CI: \$41–1,096)	\$394 (CI: \$39–1,038)	

Note: Avoided premature mortality totals underlying these estimates use model-averaged PM_{2.5} concentration changes and the exposure–response function from Burnett et al. (27).

^aFederal tax credit net expenditures from Jenkins et al. (3), as reported in Bistline et al. (36). ^bDirect spending on climate-related programs and reduced public revenue from tax credit programs from the Congressional Budget Office (35).

Table S4. Avoided PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths by race/ethnicity, year, and scenario.

Year	Scenario	Mortality rate stratification	Racial/ethnic group				
			Asian	Black	Hispanic	Native	White
2035	IRA	Unstratified	398 (5.7%)	794 (11.5%)	802 (11.6%)	30 (0.43%)	4,907 (70.8%)
		Stratified	272 (4.0%)	890 (13.0%)	685 (10.0%)	24 (0.36%)	4,982 (72.7%)
	Net Zero	Unstratified	424 (5.0%)	968 (11.5%)	891 (10.6%)	36 (0.42%)	6,114 (72.5%)
		Stratified	287 (3.4%)	1,083 (13.0%)	755 (9.0%)	29 (0.34%)	6,193 (74.2%)
2050	IRA	Unstratified	599 (10.0%)	776 (12.9%)	1,062 (17.7%)	26 (0.43%)	3,546 (59.0%)
		Stratified	424 (7.3%)	804 (13.9%)	930 (16.1%)	20 (0.34%)	3,614 (62.4%)
	Net Zero	Unstratified	1,378 (7.8%)	2,266 (12.8%)	2,878 (16.3%)	78 (0.44%)	11,046 (62.6%)
		Stratified	957 (5.6%)	2,352 (13.8%)	2,505 (14.7%)	57 (0.34%)	11,215 (65.6%)

Note: Values shown here use model-averaged concentration data and the exposure–response function from Burnett et al. (27).

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